

Online Game Addiction among *Mobile Legends*'s Players

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Abstract—The aim of this research is to measure online game addiction levels of *Mobile Legends*'s players. This research uses a descriptive statistical approach involved 375 participants that taken by incidental sampling. Participants in this research are young adults that play *Mobile Legends* at least 3 hours a day. The result shows three levels of online game addiction in *Mobile Legend*'s players. There are 66 participants on mild level of addiction, 236 participants on moderate level of addiction and 73 participants on severe level of addiction. It means most of participants in this research are on moderate level of online game addiction. This findings can be used as a guide to make further research about online game addiction.

Keywords—Addiction, online game and mobile legends.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, many people using online game as their amusement. They can access online game from their mobile phone whenever they have a time or stress about their life. Online game has become an important issue in Indonesia, Internet World Stats (2017) shows that Indonesia is in the fifth position with the most internet users in the world. Surveys about online game player show that 54.13% users are children to adults, which most users are 13 to 18 years old, and the second rank are 19 to 34 years old (Asosiasi Jasa Penyelenggara Internet Indonesia, 2017).

One of the most popular online game is MultiplayerOnlineBattleArena (MOBA), which is about two teamsthat get into battle.Each team has five members with diffrent avatars and skills. All teams have a mission to control and destroy the enemy's base to finish the game (Tyack, Wyeth, & Johnson, 2016). Many people tend to play this game because it has a high level of challenge (Johnson, Nacke, & Wyeth, 2015) and high competition where players want to gain strength, wealth and quickly experience changes in the game, which then triggers intense competition and does not want to be defeated by co-star (Yee, 2006). In this game users can collaborate virtually, improve cognitive abilities and critical thinking, learn to control emotions, practice foresight and do not easily give up (Mahyuddin, 2018).

One of most popular MOBA is *Mobile Legends*. There are 49.98 million users out of 170 million active *Mobile Legends* players coming from Indonesia (Alfarizi & Mahbub, 2019). Wherever we go, we will be able to see individuals or groups of people who are playing *Mobile Legends* together for a long time. According to Young & Abreu (2011), users that using the internet 20-80 hours per week, can be called addicted users. Online game addiction according to Griffiths (2005) is a

behavior that involves an active interaction between humans and online game. Addicted users exhibit the dependency behavior both in feeling and mind to the online game, run away from problems into online games, increased usage time in online games, feel unhappy when online gaming activities are interrupted, get into trouble due to playing online games and a tendency to repeat the same pattern of playing online games after the stop phase. Adult individuals tend to be able to control their behavior compared to adolescents because this ability developed in adolescence such as making the right decisions, monitoring behavior and the ability to deal with problems (Murray & Rosanbalm, 2017). In fact, many adult individuals who also plays *Mobile Legend* for a long time.

II. OBJECTION AND METHOD

The main objective of this study is to measure the online game addiction levels in *Mobile Legends*'s players. Participants in this study were taken by using incidental sampling involving 375 adults, ranged from aged 19-34 years old, and actively playing *Mobile Legends* for at least 3 hours every day. The instrument is online game addiction scale that modified from the internet addiction scale constructed by Sari (2019) based on Griffiths's internet addiction theory (2005). The scale is arranged with a Likert scale type which is consisting of five answer choices: Absolutely Agree (AA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Not Agree (NA), and Absolutely Not Agree (ANA). The scores moved from 1 to 5, and the scales were presented in the form of statements of favorable (support) and unfavorable (not support). The data were analyzed by descriptive statistics.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that online game addiction consists of 3 levels of addiction, such as mild, moderate, severe (Young, 1998). Table 1 shows the frequency of *Mobile Legends* users based on the level of addiction they experienced.

Level	Frequency	Percentase
Mild	66	17.6%
Moderate	236	62.9%
Severe	73	19.5%

Table 1 shows that 66 participants had mild addiction, 236 participants had moderate addiction, and 73 participants had severe addiction. This result shows that most

of participants are on the moderate level of addiction. According to Young (1998), participant who had moderate addiction level tend to experience some problem in their life, either work problems, physical and psychological, and also their social life. There are several things that can be the cause of online game addiction in adults. Their addiction develops as a “consequence of life events, such as divorce, lay-off, and unemployment”, which leads to “retreat into the virtual world”. Adults seek refuge from the sometimes harsh (offline) life and may find that online, life is so much easier as they are able to achieve their goals more quickly and their game keeps them occupied and deceptively happy (Kuss & Griffiths, 2015).

In addition, this study also gathered data of gender and the amount of time they spent playing *mobile legends*. The results show that there were 87 females and 288 males who played *mobile legends*. This results also show that there were 231 participants who play for 3 hours/day, 113 who play for 3 to 5 hours/day and 31 participants who play for more than 5 hours/day.

The significant difference between the number of females and males in this study is in line with the statement of Kuss & Griffiths (2015) who found that males tend to use the internet more for online gaming compared to females. When compared with females, the development of social competence of males is not so well developed during adolescence that they are more vulnerable to engaging in online games. And also, that males live out their need for belongingness and for proving oneself via the Internet rather than through real-life accomplishments. They look up to the successful and renowned pro-gamer, who has now replaced the father as ultimate role model. Males strive for something different than they used to a couple of decades ago. Coupled with the *uncanny* requirements of many online games, sociocultural changes and inadequate paragons of masculinity increase the risk for Internet addiction in males (Kuss & Griffiths, 2015).

IV. CONCLUSION

This study aims to measure online game addiction level in *mobile legends* players. Most of participants in this research is on moderate online game addiction, which is the individuals begin to experience several conflicts in their life and consider that online games as an important part of their life.

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